

Supplementary Materials

Limits of lockdown: characterising essential contacts during strict physical distancing

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Supplementary Figure 1: Frequency of questionnaire responses. Responses received during the rollout period of 9th April 2020 to 14th May 2020; peaks coincide with invitation and reminder emails

Supplementary Figure 2: Model fit comparison. Model fit plotted for negative binomial (NegBin), its zero inflated equivalent (Zinb) and observed counts. Proportion of observed zeros: 2825/6807 (41.5%); proportion of predicted zeros for negative binomial: 2881/6807 (42.3%) and zero inflated negative binomial: 2931/6807 (43.1%). Number of contacts truncated at 50.

Supplementary Table 1: Characteristics of questionnaire participants in comparison to the South West and UK population. Population estimates provided by ONS 2019 mid-year and 2011 census estimates

Characteristic*	Questionnaire participants		ONS South West estimate	ONS UK estimate
	n	(%)	(%)	(%)
Sex	6807			
Female	4895	71.9	50.8	50.6
Male	1912	28.1	49.2	49.4
Age†	6807			
23–29	3039	44.6	12.9	13.1
30–39	45	0.7	16.1	18.8
40–49	90	1.3	16.4	17.8
50–59	2107	31.0	19.3	19.2
60–69	1455	21.4	16.4	15.0
70+	71	1.0	18.9	16.1
Ethnicity‡	6177			
Non-white	137	2.2	4.7	12.9
White	6040	97.8	95.3	87.1
Unknown	630			

*Data for sex and age from the ONS 2019 mid-year estimates [1]

†No participants were aged under 23 years of age, percentages of age groups in the observed sample only were compared to ONS data. The 70+ age group was censored at 85.

‡Ethnicity data from the 2011 census for South West and UK populations [2]

References

1. Office-for-National-Statistics. Office for National Statistics. Population estimates for the UK, England and Wales, Scotland and Northern Ireland: mid-2019, using April 2020 local authority district codes. 2021
2. Office-for-national-statistics. Census 2011. KS201 UK, Ethnic group. 2011.